

Micellar catalysis – A kinetic study of polymerization of *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide

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The kinetics of polymerization of *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (MBA), using V^V -cyclohexanone (CHN) redox initiator, in presence of cationic surfactants *N*-cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide (CTAB) and tetrabutylammoniumbromide (TBAB), has been studied at 303 K. The rate of polymerization (R_p) increases with increasing concentration of CTAB and TBAB above their critical micellar concentration (CMC). R_p is found to be proportional to $[MBA]^2$, $[V^V]$ and $[CHN]$. The R_p increases with increase in $[V^V]$, which results in a high molecular weight polymer. A mechanism involving both linear and mutual termination steps is proposed.

Vinyl polymerization is catalyzed by both anionic and cationic micelles. Micelles interact with metal ion which in turn influence the rate of polymerization^{1,2}. Recently Patra and Sinha³ reported an account of metal ion influence on the micellar catalysis of Ce^{IV} initiated polymerization of methyl acrylate. The free radicals generated by metal ion-substrate combination initiate polymerization⁴. This can also be brought about by means of several other initiators⁵.

The nature of the electrostatic interaction between the micelle and the metal ion decides the type of termination step. This termination step influences the molecular weight of the resulting polymer. The systems, which produce polymers of high molecular weight, have great industrial utility^{6,7}. The interesting and useful mechanical properties that are uniquely associated with polymeric materials are a consequence of their molecular weight. Hence control of molecular weight is essential for the practical application of polymerization process. The control of molecular weight and molecular weight distribution (MWD) is often used to obtain and improve certain desired physical properties in a polymer product. V^V is a well known oxidant, which in combination with a reductant, initiates polymerization and also participates in the termination step⁸. Cationic micelles such as *N*-cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide (CTAB) and tetrabutylammoniumbromide (TBAB) are chosen in the present study to test a system, in which mutual termination is expected resulting in high molecular weight polymers. Hence the present kinetic study of polymerization of *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (MBA), in the presence of micellar phase of CTAB and TBAB, initiated by V^V -cyclohexanone, is taken up to test whether linear or mutual termina-

tion takes place. Also it is intended to evaluate the efficacy of CTAB and TBAB as catalysts.

Results and discussion

CTAB and TBAB catalysis of polymerization of MBA :

Effect of $[V^V]$ on R_p :

In the absence of micelle, the rate of polymerization decreases with increase in $[V^V]$ with a linear termination step⁹. But in the present case, the rate of polymerization increases with increase in the concentration of V^V which suggests either the possibility of linear/mutual terminations. If only mutual termination takes place the order in $[V^V]$ would have been 0.5. But in the present study the order in $[V^V]$ was found to be 0.85 and 0.91 in the case of CTAB (Fig. 1) and TBAB systems, respectively. This shows that both mutual and linear terminations take place. The hydrophilic nature of metal ion permits them to reach only the Stern layer. A few of these metal ions manage to enter their micellar cavities¹⁰, where the organic monomer (MBA) units concentrate due to hydrophobic nature of micelle. This decreases the possibility of linear termination.

Effect of $[MBA]$ on R_p :

Rate of polymerization increases with increase in $[MBA]$. The order in $[MBA]$ was found to be 1.93 and 1.91 in the case of CTAB and TBAB catalysis, respectively. This shows that both linear and mutual termination steps are involved in the mechanism. In the micellar phase the increased rate of polymerization is due to the possible accumulation of monomer molecules in the micellar cavities which provide a conducive atmosphere for polymerization.

Fig. 1. (A) Order in $[V^V]$; $3 + \log R_p$ vs $2 + \log [V^V]$. (B) Order in $[MBA]$; $4 + \log R_p$ vs $2 + \log [MBA]$. (C) Order in $[CHN]$; $4 + \log R_p$ vs $\log [CHN]$. $[V^V] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[MBA] = 0.06 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[CHN] = 0.48 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; CTAB = 0.01 mol dm^{-3} ; temp. = 303 K.

Effect of $[CHN]$ on R_p :

Increase in $[CHN]$ increases the rate of polymerization. The order in $[CHN]$ was found to be 1.1 and 0.92 in the case of CTAB (Fig. 1) and TBAB catalysis respectively. The order in $[CHN]$ shows that both linear and mutual terminations occur.

Effect of [micelle] on R_p :

The kinetics of polymerization of MBA using V^V -CHN system in the presence of cationic micelles CTAB and TBAB has been carried out at 303 K. These results are presented in Table 1.

Surfactant in aqueous medium, beyond the critical micellar concentration (CMC), aggregates to form micelle. This results in a biphasic system, namely the bulk phase and the micellar phase. Due to hydrophobic interaction of surfactants, the monomers get solubilised in micelles. In the present case CTAB and TBAB are cationic micelles which experience electrostatic attractions with the negatively charged meta vanadate ions. This results in an increase in the metal ion concentration in the Stern layer.

Table 1. Variation of R_p with [micelle]

[Micelle] $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3}	$R_p \times 10^{-3}$ with CTAB	$R_p \times 10^{-3}$ with TBAB
0	0.04	0.02
10	3.38	2.90
15	4.60	3.20
20	5.20	3.90
25	7.40	4.60

$[V^V] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[CHN] = 0.48 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[MBA] = 0.06 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. 303 K.

The free-radical formed by the V^V -CHN redox couple in the Stern layer enters the micellar cavity and initiates the polymerization. The rate of polymerization (R_p) increases with increase in $[\text{micelle}]$ (Table 1). Patra and Singh¹¹ reported similar kinetic data in the ceric ion initiated graft copolymerization of acrylonitrile and methylmethacrylate by the influence of *N*-acetyl glycine. In the present study the rate is found to be higher in presence of CTAB as compared to that of TBAB (Table 1). This observed difference may be due to the difference in CMC, which is given as per eq. (1).

$$[S_n] = (C_D - \text{CMC})/N \quad (1)$$

where C_D is the concentration of the surfactant, N is the aggregate number and $[S_n]$ is the micellar concentration¹².

However the present polymer is soluble in 1 : 8 v/v water-pyridine mixture. This goes against the formation of cross-linked polymer. Hence in the present case cyclo polymerization mechanism is operative⁹.

On the basis of the above results and discussion the following mechanism is proposed.

The rate law derived for the above scheme is given in eq. (10),

$$R_p = k_p k_i k_0 \frac{[\text{CHN}] [V^V] [MS_n]^2}{k_t + k'_t [V^V]} \quad (10)$$

where S = surfactant; S_n = micelle; M = monomer.

This rate law explains the observed kinetic results.

Determination of viscosity average-molecular weight of polymer: Average-molecular weight of the resulting polymer was measured by intrinsic viscosity method. The intrinsic viscosity was determined by Huggins and Kraemer's relation¹³. 1 : 8 v/v water-pyridine mixture was used as solvent in the viscosity measurements. The viscosity data was calculated using appropriate Mark-Houwink equation¹⁴, as per the eq. (11).

$$[\eta] = 2.82 \times 10^{-2} M_v^{0.52} \quad (11)$$

where $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic viscosity and M_v is the viscosity-average molecular weight of the polymer.

Average-molecular weight of poly (MBA) increased up to 8300 on increasing [CTAB], (0.00–0.025 M) where as it increased up to 6400 on increasing [TBAB] (0.00–0.025 M). Both the micellar catalysts CTAB and TBAB, catalyze

Table 2. Catalytic efficiency of CTAB and TBAB

Sl. no.	Catalyst used in the polymerization of MBA	$R_p \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³	Catalytic coefficient R_p/R_{p1}
1.	Nil	0.02	1.00
2.	CTAB	3.38	169
3.	TBAB	2.90	145

R_p = Rate of polymerization for catalyzed reaction, R_{p1} = rate of polymerization for uncatalyzed reaction.

the polymerization of MBA. The efficacy of the two micelles as catalysts may be compared from the data given in Table 2.

It can be seen that CTAB has a higher catalytic coefficient of 169 (Table 2) as compared to that of TBAB with a catalytic coefficient of 145. Hence CTAB is a better catalyst than TBAB in the polymerization of MBA.

In the present study two micelles CTAB and TBAB have been tested to be good facilitators for mutual termination in the V^V -CHN-MBA system resulting in high molecular weight polymer.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. V^V solutions were prepared by adding previously weighed amounts of ammonium metavanadate in sulphuric acid of known strength and the concentration estimated by titrating against standard ferrous solution. Commercial MBA (E. Merck) was purified by recrystallization from water. Cyclohexanone was distilled just before use. Commercial CTAB and TBAB (E. Merck) were used as such. The experimental procedure employed for following the rate of polymerization (R_p) is same as that followed by Rao *et al.* and Mishra *et al.*¹⁵.

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